

Theoretical basics of negative environmental impact reduction of water-born transportation vessels

Vasily Konstantinovich Novikov ^{1,§} and Victoria Alexandrovna Kuzmichova ^{1,◇}

¹Moscow State Academy of Water Transport, the branch of federal state budgetary institution of higher education, “Admiral S. O. Makarov State University of Maritime and River Fleet” (MGAVT, branch of FGBOU VO “Admiral S. O. Makarov GUMRF”). 125993, Moscow, Petrovka 3/6, Russia.

To cite this article:

Vasily Konstantinovich Novikov and Victoria Alexandrovna Kuzmichova. “Theoretical basics of negative environmental impact reduction of water-born transportation vessels”, *Parana Journal of Science and Education*. Vol. 6, No.4, 2020, pp. 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3880454>

Received: April 16, 2020; **Accepted:** May 20, 2020; **Published:** June 5, 2020.

Abstract

The results are presented of the theoretical research on possible ways of the environmental burden reduction in operation of the water-born transportation vessels (WT). It is shown that the operation of the sea and river vessels is accompanied by the increased environmental load due to the following factors: the oil-containing water discharges (OW); the discharges of garbage, effluents (or waste water, WW); ballast water containing undesired organisms; the emission of the exhaust gases (EG) containing oxides of sulfur and nitrogen; the emission of the volatile organic compounds (JIOC) at loading/unloading/transporting the raw oil and the petroleum products; the oil spills as a result of emergency situations; the port jams of passenger/cargo, servicing and auxiliary vessels, boats and motor yachts, which inflicts the oil pollution of the entire ports waters and large aquatic areas around; etc. For the permissible regulatory pollutants discharges and releases from ships, the international and domestic values are given, abiding of which will reduce the environmental load of the WT vessels operation significantly. The main possible measures to reduce the environmental burden of the WT vessels operation are as follows: reducing of the WW discharge; liquidation and disposal of OW and garbage; EG danger reduction; use of the liquefied natural gas (LNG) as fuel for the internal combustion engines (ICE).

Keywords: Ship, Vessel, Water-born transportation, Environmental load, Reduction.

§ Email: VKNovikov@yandex.ru

◇ Email: vicka.cu@yandex.ru

¥ Email: valery_morozov@hotmail.com (Corresponding). Valery Borisovich Morozov[¥], Russian Academy of Sciences, Lebedev Physical Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 53, Leninskiy Prospekt, 119991, Moscow, Russia.

1. Introduction

Always, human activities affect the environment; however until the XX century, this influence was rather invisible due to the biosphere's ability of the self-restoration. But as early as at the beginning of the XX century, the scientific and technological progress resulted in the humanity's awareness of the solving necessity of the problems associated with the extremely negative environmental changes caused by the human activities. This brought the society to the realization that many processes of the human activity lead to changes in the biosphere of such a scale that the problems become global.

The use of the variety of vehicles including the WT vessels supporting the human activity processes makes certain "contribution" to the growth of the environmental load, which is expressed in the following facts [1]:

- The consumption increase of the natural resources including as follows: the atmospheric air used in the work processes of the ICE engines; the petroleum products and natural gas being the fuel for the ICE engines; the water used for ICE cooling systems and industrial and household needs on ships; etc.;
- The pollution of the atmosphere, the water basins and the lithosphere; the generation of wastes.

In addition, the transportation sector of the economics is characterized by the heat release to the environment in the ICE engines operation; the noise and vibration generation of high levels; the people's injuries/deaths and the damage of goods being transported, etc. Due to these dangers, an urgent necessity is aroused in the state analysis of the negative environmental load of the WT vessels. It is needed to identify the main causes and sources of its occurrence, which would become the basis for development of possible ways to reduce the harm.

2. Development

This paper is aimed at development of theoretical basics of possible reduction of the environmental burden caused by the WT vessels.

The environmental pressure is the anthropogenic impact on the environment components, which leads or may lead to their quality deterioration. This applies to the WT vessels in full. The

essence and content of the main components of the environmental burden due to the production and operation of the WT vessels are given below: [1]

2.1 Consumption of natural resources

In addition to the material and labor resources, many types of the natural resources are required for the processes of the production and operation of the WT vessels. Notably, the nature management is conducted in three directions:

- Expenditure of the natural resources. It covers their extraction and further processing including impurities removal, resources transformation into a desired form and their use. Among such consumable natural resources, there are the atmospheric air, water, land resources and the raw materials (oil, gas, coal, minerals, wood) that are used for the production and operation of the ships and the facilities they service;
- Use of natural conditions (climatic and water-related conditions, land relief, etc.) and ways of making influence on them;
- Issues of the balance disturbance of the natural systems and their protection during the vessels operation. In the natural systems, a balance should be maintained of many environmental components (energy, gases, water, plants-producers, animals-consumers and organisms-decomposers).

2.2 Environment pollution

The process of the environment pollution by the WT vessels is summarized in the Table (1) [2].

2.2.1 Effluents, wastewaters

During the vessels operation, while using water for drinking and household needs, the WW waters are accumulated [2-3].

The effluents consist of the following contents:

- Drains and other wastes from all types of toilets, urinals and toilet bowls;
- Drains from sinks, bathtubs, and scuppers;
- Drains from premises, where animals are kept.

In general, the ship effluents contain organic and mineral substances, various microorganisms and suspended impurities. For the hygienic assessment of WW waters, the following indicators have been

adopted: biochemical oxygen demand (BOD); chemical oxygen demand (COD); suspended materials concentration (SMC); hydrogen index (pH); lacto-positive coli bacilli count (LCB); microbe colony count (MCC); transparency (in cm); chromaticness (in degrees).

2.2.1 Oily waters

The OW effluents on the WT vessels are formed from waters accumulated under the flooring of engine rooms and containing petroleum products as a result of water leaks from pipelines, fittings and pumps through deadwood devices, hull plating and bottom fittings, as well as those oil products leaks from pipelines and fittings that are formed during a repair of mechanisms of fuel and oil equipment.

The OW contains fuel up to 70-80 %, oil up to 20-30 % and mechanical impurities up to 4 -6 %. The average amount of oil contained in the OW is at least 2000 rpm in the case of the diesel-powered vessels and 1500 rpm in the case of the steam-turbine-powered vessels [2-3].

Household, food and operational wastes occur on ships because of production and household activities of crewmembers and passengers [2, 3]. The household waste includes empty things used earlier as containers or packing materials and diverse wastes made of all types of plastics, paper, textiles, glass and metal. The food waste is the type of garbage consisting of wastes resulted from edibles' pre-cooking processing and unused residues. The operational waste is waste generated because of production and repair works performed on ships.

Table 1 - Formation of environment pollution during ships operation.

Source of pollution	Pollutant	Contaminated medium
Personal and household needs of crew members and passengers	WW, solid residues and garbage.	Water
Ships' main and auxiliary mechanisms and systems	Exhaust gases (EG)	Atmospheric air
	Solid residues and garbage, OW (oil leaks with bilge water, oil residues, ballast and wash water).	Water
Cargos and ship basement stores	Gases, sewage steams	Atmospheric air
	Solid residues and garbage, oil residues with ballast and wash water.	Water

Source: [2].

2.3 Exhaust gases

The main causes of the atmospheric pollution by ships are the marine engines, main and auxiliary ones. The EG of a ship power plant (SPP) contains about 200 components. Based on a nature of an impact on the human body as well as a chemical structure and properties of main components, the EG are divided into seven main groups [2, 3]:

- I. non-toxic substances such as nitrogen N₂, oxygen O₂, hydrogen H₂, water vapor H₂O as well as carbon dioxide CO₂;
- II. monoxide carbon CO;
- III. oxides NO_x;
- IV. hydrocarbons C_nH_m;
- V. aldehydes (formaldehyde and acrolein);
- VI. soot (its content can characterize the smokiness);
- VII. benzo(a)pyrene. Also, when using a sulfur fuel, the EG includes sulfur anhydrite SO₂ and hydrogen sulfide H₂S; notably, under

certain conditions, these substances form the sulfurous and sulfuric acids.

The components N₂, O₂, H₂O and CO₂ make up 99 to 99.9% of the gas volume, while the

remaining 0.1-1.0% of the volume contains impurities that are also harmful to the environment. The summary data on the EG composition is presented in the Table (2) [3, 4].

Table 2 - EG composition and impact on environment.

EG Component	Component value*	Property of polluted air
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	040 - 240	Suffocating effect
Sulfur dioxide (SO ₂)	0.1 - 2.5	Toxicity
Monoxide carbon (CO)	0.25 - 2.50	Toxicity
Acrolein (CH ₂ CHCHO)	0.001 - 0.040	Toxicity
Nitrogen oxides NO _x (on NO ₂)	0.5 - 0.8	Toxicity
Hydrocarbons C _n H _m (on C)	0.25 - 2.00	Toxicity
Soot	0.05 - 1.00	Toxicity, Opacity
Water vapor (H ₂ O)	015 - 100	Fogging
Benzo(a)pyrene	0.02 - 0.05	Carcinogenic effect
Formaldehydes (HCOH)	0.02 - 0.40	Irritation of respiratory tract

Note: *(g/m³). **Source:** [2-3].

An amount of harmful emissions contained in EG depends on whether or not fuel combustion is complete, on fuel quality, additives presence, SPP design characteristics, a temperature regime, fuel atomization, a level of servicing and an operation mode.

2.4 Ways to eliminate pollutants generated on ship

In the Russian River Register and SanPiN 2.5.2-703-98, the following two methods have been identified for marine pollutants elimination:

- Wastes transfer to off-ship (onshore or floating) water protection equipment;
- Recycling and/or disposal of wastes directly on the same vessel board with aid of shipboard equipment units (WW cleaning and decontamination stations (WWCD), OW cleaning stations (OWC) and furnaces (boilers) - incinerators.

A choice of a particular method depends on the navigation area, the number and capacity of wastes reception facilities on the shore, the vessel type, the number of people on board, the requirements for disposal of processed and untreated WW and garbage, the availability and

number of the collection vessels and the vessels of integrated waste processing.

2.5 Regulation for discharges and releases of pollutants from ships

In the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships MARPOL-73/78, the requirements are defined for effluents discharge from vessels with a gross capacity of more than 200 register ton as well as from all vessels with more than 10 people on board. In particular, it is specified that in any coastal zone 12 nautical miles wide, the effluents discharge be prohibited unless they are previously cleaned and decontaminated up to the following parameters' values:

- ❖ BOD₅ (in mg O₂/dm³) = 50;
- ❖ suspended solids (x is amount of suspended substances in the wash water measured in mg/dm³) = 100+x;
- ❖ Coli index (in pcs/dm³) = 2 500.

In the 4-nautical-mile-wide coastal zone, the WW dumping is completely prohibited including the purified effluents.

In the MARPOL-73/78, it is determined that the OW discharge is allowed in the case of the compliance with the following conditions: the ship is located outside a “special area”; the ship is situated in a distance of more than 12 nautical miles from the nearest shore; the ship is on its way; the oil content in the effluents is less than 100 mg/dm³; the ship is fitted with the following equipment being in the working order: a system of automatic measurement, registration and management of oil discharge, an equipment for oil-water separation and an oil filtration system. However, these conditions may not be met if the concentration of the oil in the effluents does not exceed 15 mg/dm³.

The rules written in the Russian River Register define the standardized quality indicators of WW and OW for WT vessels, Table (3). When a ship is parked in a port, any effluents release is prohibited including the purified WW. It is prohibited to discharge WW and OW, when vessels are parked within sections of waterways declared to be national parks/reserves (in accordance with the established procedure), in areas of mass fish spawning, in areas of sanitary protection of drinking water sources and in places of mass water use for the human population needs.

Table 3 – Standardized indicators of WW and OW.

Standardized indicator	Limit value of indicator	
	On inland waterways	At sea
Oil content in the discharge, mg/dm ³	8	15
Suspended solids, mg/dm ³	40	100
Coli-index, coli titers/dm ³	1000	2500
Residual chlorine (during chlorine disinfection, mg/dm ³)	3	-
BOD ₅ , mg O ₂ /dm ³	40	50

Source: [2-3].

Table 4 – Threshold limit values of standardized parameters for new diesels.

Standardized parameter name	Denomination	Norm of specific weighted average emissions of marine diesel engines		
		Production year before 2000	Production year after 2000	After capital repairs
Specific weighted average emission of nitrogen oxides (NO _x) normalized to NO ₂ , g/kWh	NO _x	17.0	17.0 - 9.8	0.95
Weighted average of specific emissions of carbon monoxide (CO), g/kWh	CO	6.0	3.0	1.20
Weighted average of specific emissions of hydrocarbons (CH) normalized to CH1.85, g/kWh	CH	2.4	1.0	1.25

Note: at the rotation speed of $n \leq 130$ rpm, NO_x = 17 g/kWh; at the rotation speed of $130 < n \leq 2000$ rpm, NO_x = 45 n^{-0.2} g/kWh; at the rotation speed of $n > 2000$ rpm, NO_x = 9.8 g/kWh. **Source:** [2-3].

Depending on a specific sanitary situation in a region, local authorities of Rospotrebnadzor (Federal Service for Consumer Rights Protection and Human Welfare) may prohibit a discharge of processed WW and OW on parts of inland waterways.

Outside of the sanitary protection zones of the sources of the centralized household drinking water supply, a volley discharge of untreated WW may be allowed [5] in the cases that it is done from vessels with the number of people on board no more than 10 people, at a movement speed of at least 7 km/h; from vessels adopted the dynamic

maintenance principle with a daily accumulation of WW up to 1 m^3 moving at a speed of at least 25 km/h.

In the MARPOL-73/78, it is established that the NO_x content in EG must be 9-17 g/(kWh) depending on a crankshaft rotational speed; the smoke content is 0.15 g/m³; the carbon monoxide amount is 56 g/m³, and that of the sulfur dioxide is 6 g/(kWh). In the Russian legislation (GOST R 51249-99), the emissions of harmful substances from diesels are regulated for nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon oxides (CO) and hydrocarbons (CH), Table (4).

The smokiness standards of EG emission for the marine diesels are given in the GOST R 51250-99, where the maximum permissible values of the parameters are given depending on the conditional EG flow at any steady state.

3. Environmental impact

3.1 Possible measures for reduction of ships environmental impact

WW release reduction. The WW amount on ships depends directly on the water consumption. Therefore, it is possible to reduce the WW-caused environmental impact of a ship by the water consumption reduction or the on-board recycling systems use. At reducing of water consumption, it is necessary to reduce the flow of water (running through the water-collecting valves of the galley, shower rooms, washrooms and toilets) and to improve the valves design: by throttling the flow of water at various pressures on the decks (2-3% water savings); by reducing the idle time (up to 30% water savings); etc. The development of the on-board recycling systems is even more interesting from the point of view of their introduction feasibility on ships. Being installed just on board, the recycling systems can be used for supplying systems, where the process water is clean enough: for flushing toilets, for feeding the low-pressure boilers with water, for SPP cooling and power systems, and for gas purification plants.

In addition, it is possible to reduce the water consumption (especially in the hot season) by artificial favorable climate creating in residential and office premises with aid of air conditioning systems and by an introduction of small swimming pools on board. Both of these proposals will reduce the consumption of drinking

quality water in showers dramatically and thus reduce the amount of the WW.

3.2 Elimination and disposal of OW and garbage

With due consideration of the high cost, weight and dimensions of the OW purification equipment, it is advisable to use OW after pretreatment in WFE (water-fuel emulsion) for boilers and incinerators [6]. In addition, this measure will reduce the amount of harmful substances in EG. Equipping of large and medium-sized vessels with incinerators would solve the problem of destroying and – if certain conditions are met – disposing of major types of the garbage.

3.3 EG hazard reduction for the environment

Mechanisms of formation of various toxic substances in composition of EG released by SPP have fundamental differences, so it is impossible to reduce the EG amount with aid of any universal means. In practice, the solution to this problem is found in two directions: making the gases less harmful during their formation and the processed EG toxicity reduction.

For unstable modes of ICE engines, the most significant reduction in toxic emissions is achieved by the following measures: the gas purification, the fuel atomization (WFE), the EG recycling, the fuel pretreatment, the fuel additives use, and the transfer to alternative fuels.

The fuel additives affect the combustion process and by their nature, they are divided into two groups: the combustion intensification and the anti-smoky effect. The combustion-intensifying additives have a low energy of decomposition activation and they generate active fuel ignition centers. The more ignition initiators are contained in the fuel, the higher the cetane number is, the shorter the ignition delay period is, and the higher fuel combustion completeness is, which affects positively the fuel efficiency and reduces the emission of incomplete combustion products. Such additives include organic nitrates, nitroparaffins, organic peroxides, and esters. Upon that, the soot content is reduced by 70-90%, and the release of carcinogenic substances into the atmosphere is reduced by 60-80% [7].

The most promising way of emissions reduction of the toxic EG components into the environment is the ships park renovation with transfer to LNG use as the fuel as it is shown in the Table 5 [8].

Table 5 - Specific emissions (kg) at burning of one t fuel

Name of harmful substance	Used fuel				
	Diesel	Petroleum	Engine oil	Furnace oil	Natural gas
Sulfur oxides	3.9	0.8	23.4	40.8	-
Carbon oxides	25.6	375.0	25.6	5.3	1.53
Nitrogen oxides	68.1	83.3	68.1	10.7	8.05
Hydrocarbons	18.1	229.2	18.1	-	-
Aldehydes	0.9	10.4	0.9	-	-
Soot	6.1	1.3	6.1	-	-
Water	-	-	-	0.5	-
Benzo(a)pyrene	0.0061	0.625	0.0061	-	-

Source: [8]

4. Conclusions and proposals

- I. It was shown that the WT vessels make a quite heavy “contribution” to the environmental load growth, which is expressed in consumption of natural resources and contamination of environment components with chemical, biological and physical pollutants.
- II. The vessels operation is accompanied by the environment pollution because of OW, WW, garbage and ballast water discharges, EG emissions, JIOC emissions and oil spills.
- III. The main possible measures for the environmental load reduction of the WT vessels are as follows: the reduction of WW discharge, the correct elimination and disposal of OW and garbage, the reduction of the EG hazard, the use of the LNG as the optimal marine motor fuel.

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